

The Collapse of the Burkinabè State: Constitutional Vacuum and Crisis of Sovereignty

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The Burkinabè State, as it functioned in October 2021, is constitutionally inoperative. By failing in its fundamental sovereign duties, the government in place has disqualified itself from leading the nation. This assessment, far from being polemical, proceeds from a rigorous analysis of constitutional law applied to ground realities.

The most glaring evidence is the following: the very existence of the Burkinabè nation is in danger.

Let us look squarely, in the mirror of our collective conscience, at these realities we too often refuse to name.

I. The Constituent Elements of the State: Does Burkina Faso Still Qualify?

Every classical theory of the State rests on three fundamental elements: a territory, a population, and a sovereign political authority. Yet each of these pillars is today shaken in Burkina Faso.

On sovereignty, defined as exclusive political authority over a territory: can one seriously claim that Burkina Faso is sovereign over its entire national space? The answer, regrettably, is no.

On the nature of the State, Article 32 of the Burkinabè Constitution is unambiguous: the State is not the person of the President, but the soul of a nation. It transcends any individual, even one elected by universal suffrage. Electoral legitimacy alone cannot serve as a blank cheque for inaction or impotence.

On the unitary form of the State, Article 31 of the Constitution enshrines the unitary and indivisible character of the Republic. Yet the progressive territorial losses, land and subsoil resources removed from State control in a potentially irreversible manner, constitute a direct and serious attack on this fundamental principle.

II. State Authority Tested by the Facts

Public authority is the lifeblood of the State. How effective is it in Burkina Faso today?

The legitimacy of a political authority, however unquestionable its origin, loses all substance if it proves incapable of ensuring constitutional order across the entire national territory. An authority powerless to exercise its territorial competence cannot indefinitely invoke its formal legitimacy.

Furthermore, can a political authority violate with impunity the constitutional inviolability of its territory, with the passive complicity of the entire nation, without this constituting an existential and unforgivable dereliction of sovereign duty? The question is raised with the full gravity it deserves.

III. The “Kompetenz-Kompetenz”: Is the Burkinabè State Master of its Own Competence?

To invoke Georg Jellinek’s formulation, does the State still possess Kompetenz-Kompetenz, that is, the power to enact laws and enforce them across its entire territory, to administer justice therein, and to exercise its jurisdiction without partition?

Put more plainly: **Does the State still exist in Burkina Faso?**

IV. Democracy in Service of the Nation, Not the Other Way Around

Can a nation, and its survival, be held hostage in the name of a democratic election, by an incompetent authority that respects neither its duties, nor its commitments, nor its constitutional oaths?

A frequently misunderstood hierarchy must be restored here: it is the State and the Nation that are the objects of democracy, not the reverse. Democracy cannot take precedence over the Nation, because it is from the Nation that it draws its essence and its sovereignty. Electoral procedure is a tool in service of the common good, not an end in itself that absolves of all responsibility.

V. Accountability and Sanctions

In light of these serious failures, including those covered by Article 36 of the Constitution regarding the Head of State, the authorities concerned should be called to account before a court of justice for:

- Betrayal of oath and violation of the Constitution;
- Endangering the nation, its institutions, and its territorial integrity;
- Loss of civilian and military lives, and harm caused to their dependants;
- Moral and material damages suffered by internally displaced persons;
- Embezzlement on military procurement contracts in a time of war.

The State no longer exists in Burkina Faso. Those to whom its governance was constitutionally entrusted, along with the duties and oaths attached thereto, have violated that same Constitution. In doing so, they have broken the founding compact that binds the governed to those who govern.

In this context, a comprehensive institutional overhaul and the restoration of real and effective authority are not one option among many: they are the lesser evil.

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